

REVIEW

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A systematic review of MOOC platforms, evaluation frameworks and development of integrated model

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Abstract

Purpose The study aims to systematically evaluate studies focused on the evaluation of Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) platforms and existing frameworks to evolve an integrated model for the comprehensive evaluation of MOOC platforms.

Design/methodology/approach The study follows the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines, and the Web of Science (WoS) database was used to retrieve the data. A thematic analysis method was used to critically examine the existing frameworks identified in different studies to identify different criteria concerning various aspects of MOOC platforms. The identified criteria were further analysed to include different components concerning different aspects of MOOC platforms to propose a theoretically grounded integrated evaluation framework for MOOC platforms.

Findings The findings highlight a diverse set of evaluation frameworks used in MOOC research, including Kirkpatrick's Model, Quality Matters (QM) Evaluation Framework, and Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG). After critical analysis and discussion among peers, the study identified six major evaluation dimensions: course design and structure, learner engagement, instructional quality, assessment and learning outcomes, technical and administrative factors, and demographic and completion metrics. Furthermore, the results reveal that most MOOC research is concentrated in China, the UK and the US. Additionally, most studies employed quantitative and mixed-method approaches, with surveys being the most commonly used data-collection tool. Furthermore, xMOOC is a commonly studied platform, and the highest number of publications were published in 2024.

Originality/value The study offers a unique integrated framework by synthesizing existing MOOC evaluation frameworks, providing a practical tool for the consistent and comprehensive assessment of MOOC platforms.

Keywords MOOCs, Platforms, Evaluation framework, Systematic literature review, Online learning, Learner engagement, Course design

1 Introduction

In the current era, the knowledge economy is booming, and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has transformed the educational landscape [1–3], from traditional to virtual classrooms, and from underserved to marginalized, which has paved the way for the concept of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) [4]. MOOCs are online platforms that are geared toward large-scale participation and enable open access to education globally [5, 6]. They are designed for unlimited access and networking, which can lead to collaborative learning environments [7]. This allows people to study at their own pace and convenience [8]. By eliminating factors of place and economic matters, MOOCs aim to democratize education and appeal to a wide range of learning motivations [9, 10]. It aims to increase accessibility, encourage lifelong learning, and challenge traditional education frameworks by offering affordable and flexible alternatives [11, 12]. Its vital features include open registration, curriculum sharing, and flexible, self-paced learning [13].

Given the importance and advantages of MOOCs and their scope, coverage, unlimited access, networking, and learning environments, this transformation has democratized education and the concept of online education. Thus, the study attempts to unveil the research landscape in the domain of MOOC research and to uncover how different studies across the WoS have evaluated MOOC platforms and the frameworks or models they have utilized to conduct their studies.

However, evaluating MOOCs remains challenging [14–16]. Traditional metrics (e.g. completion or retention rates) capture only a part of the course quality [17]. The quality of a MOOC is inherently multidimensional, reflecting diverse stakeholder needs. Existing studies often focus on isolated dimensions, such as instruction or accessibility, without a unified framework to comprehensively assess platform quality. This gap underscores the need for an integrative evaluation framework that combines pedagogical, technical, and learner-centered criteria. The substantial studies identified in this domain are presented in (Table 1).

This study contributes to the MOOC literature by systematically synthesizing evaluation criteria from multiple sources into an integrated framework. Unlike previous reviews that focus on isolated aspects [18], our framework unifies the pedagogical, technical, and learner-centred dimensions. The resulting framework provides researchers and practitioners with a comprehensive tool for consistent MOOC assessments and comparisons. The study will assist them in making a choice while choosing a MOOC platform and utilising the integrated framework to evaluate MOOC platforms.

While most studies have focused on dropout prediction, discussion forums, themes, methods, contexts, MOOC learner motivation, accessibility, quality of MOOCs, types of MOOCs, language, adoption, recommender systems, and engagement, as shown in Table 1, this indicates a significant gap concerning an integrative framework. The study focuses on the evaluation criteria and framework used to evaluate MOOC Platforms and proposes a theoretically grounded integrated evaluation framework for MOOC platforms.

Table 1 Prior studies

Author	Database source	Keyword search	Articles time-span	Focus
Moore & Blackmon (2022)	Academic Search Complete and Education source	("MOOC*" OR "massive open online course*") AND ("student*" OR "learner*") AND ("perspective*" OR "experience*")	2008-2021	MOOC learner experience, motivation, course engagement, satisfaction and achievement
Cheng et al. (2022)	Scopus, Web of Science; British Education Index and ERIC	"MOOC*" AND "Chinese," "MOOCs" AND "China," "massive open online course*" AND "Chinese," "massive open online course*" AND "China,"	2012-2018	Themes, methods, contexts, new directions and trends
Chen et al. (2022)	IEEE Xplore Digital Library, ACM Digital Library, Elsevier (ScienceDirect), Wiley Online Library, Springer (SpringerLink), Taylor & Francis, Google Scholar, and Web of Science	"MOOC dropout prediction, the combination of massive online open courses and dropout prediction"	2012-2022	Dropout Prediction
Huang et al. (2023)	WEB OF SCIENCE, SCOPUS, IEEE, JSTOR, SAGE, Springer Link, and EBSCO	"For WoS: "MOOC", "higher education" and "learner OR student OR participant OR participation" For other databases: "MOOC" AND "higher education" AND "learner OR student OR participant OR participation"	2008-2021	Dropout
Almatrafi & Johri (2019)	Web of Science, Science Direct, ERIC, ACM, and IEEE Xplore	"MOOC" OR "Massiv Open Online Course" AND "forum" OR "discussion" OR "text" OR "Message" OR "thread" OR "Post" OR "Communication" OR "Interaction" OR "discourse"	2013-2017	Discussion Forum
Sanchez-Gordon & Luján-Mora (2018)	Scopus, Web of Science, Directory of Open Access Journals, and Education Resources Information Center	((MOOC OR MOOCs OR "massive open online courses") AND ("accessibility" OR "disability" OR "disabilities" OR "inclusion" OR "universal design" OR "special needs" OR "usability"))	2008-2016	Accessibility
Stracke & Trisolini (2021)	Web of Science, Scopus, Google Scholar and AlmaStart	"mooc AND quality AND pedagog*"	2013-2019	Quality of MOOCs
Hidalgo et al. (2020)	Dialnet, Google Scholar and Scopus	((MOOC OR MOOCs OR "Massive Open Online Courses" OR COMA OR "online courses") OR ("language learning" OR "English learning" OR "Foreign Language Learning" OR "second language learning" OR "language" and "MOOC" or "LMOOC"	2012-2019	Types of MOOCs, Language
Sallam et al. (2020)	Web of Science, Scopus, Ebsco Host, ProQuest, ERIC, IEEE, JSTOR	"language" and "MOOC" or "LMOOC"	2012-2018	Language of MOOCs
Shah et al. (2021)	Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar, EBSCO, JSTOR, ProQuest, Taylor & Francis, IEEE Access, Springer, Wiley Online, Emerald, Science Direct	"MOOC Adoption," "MOOC Acceptance," "MOOC Intention," and "MOOC Continuance."	2015-2021	Adoption

Table 1 (continued)

Author	Database source	Keyword search	Articles time-span	Focus
Najmani et al. (2022)	IEEE Xplore, Springer Link, Science Direct, Google Scholar, ACM Digital Library	String 1: ("MOOCs" OR "MOOC") AND ("Recommender", OR "Recommendation", OR "Recommending") AND ("System", OR "Systems") String 2: ("Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs)" OR ("Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)")) AND ("Recommender", OR "Recommendation", OR "Recommending") AND ("System", OR "Systems")	2012-2022	Recommender System

2 Review of related literature

The concept of MOOCs was first proposed in 2008 [19] to democratize education across diverse contexts, enabling individuals who are unable to access campus degree programs for various reasons [20]. It supports lifelong learning and advances one's field of practice and experience through continued upgrading [21]. MOOCs aim to make education more flexible and open by accommodating a wide range of learners, promoting innovative learning designs, and are used in the corporate sector for training and branding [22].

MOOCs are used for effective learning by enhancing engagement, promoting collaboration, and self-regulated learning [23]. They offer participants an easily achievable and lightweight method for disseminating information and developing practices [24]. Moreover, they offer global open access to educational resources and are increasingly being incorporated into blended learning environments that involve online and face-to-face teaching [25]. MOOCs enhance one-on-one interactions, create flexibility, help students understand content in their own space, and propagate cross-cultural interactions, stimulating a global perspective [26]. MOOCs are rapidly emerging and evolving fields of practice and research worldwide. The body of literature on MOOCs has increased significantly. Evaluation of MOOCs has emerged as a critical area of research that focuses on learner engagement, pedagogical effectiveness, technological infrastructure, and accessibility. Various scholars have examined different aspects of MOOCs and highlighted their benefits and challenges [27–29].

A key theme of MOOC evaluation is learner engagement and retention [30]. Studies have shown that while MOOCs attract a large number of enrolments, their completion rates remain low [31, 32]. The factors influencing engagement include course design, interactive elements and personalized feedback [33]. Researchers have emphasized that the absence of instructor presence and peer interaction negatively affects retention rates [34, 35]. Strategies such as gamification, adaptive learning, and discussion forums have been explored to enhance engagement; however, their effectiveness varies across learner demographics [36, 37].

The pedagogical framework of MOOCs has also been extensively researched. Traditional online learning theories, including constructivism and connectivism, underpin the instructional design of MOOCs [38]. However, studies have argued that significant MOOCs follow a didactic approach, limiting learner autonomy and critical thinking [39–41]. Research suggests that incorporating active learning strategies, such as project-based learning and peer assessment, can significantly improve learning outcomes [42].

Technological infrastructure plays a crucial role in effectiveness. Studies have highlighted the importance of user-friendly interfaces, mobile compatibility, and the

integration of multimedia resources [43–45]. MOOC platforms, such as Coursera, edX, and FutureLearn, provide high-quality content, but accessibility remains a challenge for learners in low-resource settings because of bandwidth constraints and language barriers [46, 47]. Emerging trends in artificial intelligence (AI) and learning analytics are being explored to provide personalized learning experiences and early interventions for struggling learners [48, 49].

Another critical aspect of MOOC evaluation is its accessibility and inclusivity. Research indicates that MOOCs often fail to accommodate learners with disabilities, leading to a significant digital divide [50, 51]. Accessibility standards, such as the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.0, are recommended to ensure inclusive learning environments [52]. Cultural diversity in MOOC content has been identified as a factor affecting learner engagement, with some studies suggesting the need for localized course content and multilingual support [53–56].

From an institutional perspective, the sustainability and scalability of MOOCs are debatable. Studies indicate that while MOOCs offer cost-effective education at scale, their financial sustainability depends on monetization strategies such as certification fees, corporate partnerships, and government funding [57–59]. Some universities leverage MOOCs for branding and outreach, whereas others integrate them into blended learning models to supplement traditional education [60]. However, concerns regarding return on investment and long-term viability persist [61].

Despite extensive research on MOOCs, gaps remain in the comprehensive evaluation of MOOC platforms, particularly in the frameworks and criteria used to evaluate existing MOOC platforms. Existing studies have focused on completion and retention rates, cost-effectiveness [5], assessment type, teacher-learner interaction, learner-learner interaction [62], dropout rates [63], discussion forums [64], and learner motivation [65]. However, systematic syntheses of the evaluation criteria are lacking [66]. Few studies have holistically evaluated MOOC platforms, considering technological infrastructure [67], learner engagement and satisfaction [68], and demographics [69]. Wang R, Cao J, Xu Y, Li Y note that few systematic reviews have addressed learner engagement in MOOCs, indicating a broader gap in comprehensive MOOC evaluation [70]. After a thorough review of the literature, the authors found that no prior study has integrated diverse evaluation frameworks into a single framework. Therefore, this study focuses on the evaluation criteria and frameworks used to assess MOOC platforms and develops a theoretically grounded integrated evaluation framework for comprehensive platform evaluation.

Addressing this gap is crucial for enhancing the effectiveness and sustainability of MOOCs in an evolving digital educational landscape. Thus, through the existing literature survey, the present study identified the following research questions to reveal different dimensions of the MOOCs ecosystem for effective implementation and evaluation of MOOC platforms in different settings using a systematic literature review (SLR).

2.1 Research questions

RQ1. What theoretical models or frameworks are used in MOOC-related research?

RQ2. Which specific MOOC platforms have been studied thus far?

RQ3. What is the geographical context of MOOC-related research?

RQ4. What are the trends in MOOC research?

RQ5. What specific metrics are used to evaluate MOOC platforms?

RQ6. Is a qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-method approach employed?

RQ7. What tools or instruments were used to gather data?

3 Research framework and methodology of SLR

3.1 Search strategy and data collection

The study utilized the WoS database and followed the PRISMA guidelines [71]. The PRISMA 2020 statement [72] was followed to ensure a transparent and replicable review protocol. PRISMA provides a detailed checklist and flow diagram to guide study selection and reporting, which enhances the rigor of systematic reviews in educational research. Researchers began by searching for all published studies related to MOOC evaluations. To select relevant keywords, the authors thoroughly scanned papers published in the domain. After the consensus of all the authors, keywords such as “MOOC”, “evaluation”, “criteria”, and “framework” in the titles, summaries, or keywords of studies were considered, and the following search strings were used to harvest the relevant data: *((TS=(MOOC* OR “Massive Open Online Course*”) OR AB=(MOOC* OR “Massive Open Online Course*”)) AND (TS=(Evaluation OR Criteria OR Framework OR Assessment) OR AB=(Evaluation OR Criteria OR Framework OR Assessment)))*.

The time range was set from 01-01-2008 to 01-02-2025, the language as English, and research articles (not opinion pieces or blogs) the search was executed on 1st February 2025 and a total of 904 articles were retrieved.

3.2 Initial data screening and duplicate removal

After successful data harvesting, duplicates and retracted articles (104 studies) and studies that did not seem relevant (716 studies) were removed as the scope of these articles did not align with the research questions of this study. In the next stage, the authors scanned the titles and narrowed the search results to obtain a result-oriented corpus. Furthermore, in the next stage, the authors started abstract screening with a focus on excluding studies that did not discuss MOOC platform evaluation. The strategic refinement of data through the above stages led to the exclusion of 820 studies and the selection of only 84 studies for full-text assessment.

3.3 Full-text review and final selection

The researchers then downloaded and read the full texts of these 84 studies carefully to ensure that they fit the scope and answered the research questions of the study. Finally, 44 studies were excluded, and only 40 studies were retained, meeting the inclusion criteria framed in accordance with the research questions.

3.4 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The authors adhered to the criteria that this systematic literature review included studies that discussed how MOOCs are evaluated, including frameworks, criteria, and assessment methods. Only English-language research articles were included. Studies that did not address the evaluation of MOOCs, even if they discussed online courses, were excluded. Studies with unclear goals and poorly explained results were also excluded from the analysis. Books, chapters, and conference proceedings were also excluded.

The coding process was initiated following this step.

3.5 Quality assessment and coding process

To ensure that the selected studies were trustworthy, the study used a checklist by Boynton and Greenhalgh [73]. The checklist includes questions such as, Was the study’s goal clear? Did they collect the data properly? Were these results explained?

3.6 Data compilation and validation

Finally, after compiling the dataset, the authors examined the dataset wherever there was any confusion or query, which was resolved after mutual agreement and logical understanding. Following these steps, the study ensured that the review was fair, thorough, and focused on the best available information. A flowchart depicting the process and framework of this review is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 PRISMA flow chart.

Source: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>; <https://www.prisma-statement.org/prisma-2020-flow-diagram>

4 Results and data analysis

4.1 Descriptive results

RQ1. What theoretical models or frameworks are used in MOOC-related research?

Table 2 presents an analysis of the evaluation frameworks in the reviewed MOOC studies, revealing significant diversity in the approaches. Twenty distinct frameworks were identified, with Kirkpatrick’s Model and the Quality Matters Evaluation Framework each cited in three studies, reflecting their prominence in assessing training effectiveness and course quality. Additionally, some studies adopted hybrid frameworks, such as combining Kirkpatrick’s Model with the RE-AIM Model (two studies), to integrate complementary evaluation perspectives. The focus on accessibility and inclusivity was evident through the use of standards such as WCAG 2.1 and Universal Design for Learning (two studies), which address usability and equitable access. Moreover, the fact that 16 frameworks were referenced only once underscores the fragmented nature of evaluation practices, while 14 of the 40 reviewed studies did not align with any named framework, indicating a reliance on ad hoc, context-specific methodologies and the need for future standardization.

RQ2. Which specific MOOC platforms have been studied thus far?

Figure 2 summarizes the distribution of MOOC types identified in the reviewed literature. A total of nine distinct MOOC classifications were documented, with XMOOCs being the predominant type, accounting for 16 instances; however, another category, “All Types,” which highlights MOOCs in general, accounts for 16 instances, and IR MOOCs accounts for two instances. Other notable categories include BMOOCs, CMOOCs, and hybrid or overlapping classifications such as CMOOC, XMOOC, FP MOOC, and ICS

Table 2 Frameworks used in the reviewed studies

Framework	Numbers of papers used
Kirkpatrick’s Model	3
Quality Matters (QM) Evaluation Framework	3
Kirkpatrick’s, Re-Aim Model	2
Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1	2
Adaptive, Emergent Evaluation Inquiry Framework	1
Azevedo, Marques Framework	1
CONOLE’S 12 DIMENSIONS RUBRICS, ISONORM 9241/110-S (For Usability Evaluation)	1
Deep Learning	1
Diagnostic MOOC Evaluation(DME)	1
EduTool	1
Feed4mi	1
Grounded Theory Method (GTM)	1
Hierarchical Framework (Foundational Diversity Measures, Intermediate Indicator, Advanced Metrics)	1
Kirkpatrick’s, Re-Aim, Keppel Model	1
Ls-Sem Intelligent System	1
MOOC Evaluation Framework (MEF)	1
Multigranular Unbalanced Hesitant Fuzzy Linguistic Term Set - Multi-Attributive Border Approximation Area Comparison (MGUHFLTS-MABAC METHOD)	1
Strength Weakness Opportunity and Threats (SWOT) Analysis	1
Universal Design For Learning (UDL)	1
Universal Design For Learning (UDL), Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1, Heuristic Evaluation	1
Not Mentioned	14

Fig. 2 Types of MOOC platforms evaluated in the reviewed studies

Fig. 3 Geographical origin of the studies

MOOC, which were cited in one study each. Less common variants, such as LMOOCs, Self-Paced MOOCs, and other singularly reported types, appeared once. The diversity in classifications highlights the evolving nature of MOOC frameworks and the lack of universal standardization of terminology. The dominance of XMOOCs aligns with their widespread adoption in structured, instructor-led online education models, whereas the sparse representation of niche or blended types (for example, LMOOCs and BMOOCs) suggests opportunities for further exploration of these understudied formats.

RQ3. What is the geographical context of MOOC-related research?

Figure 3 presents the geographical distribution of the publications included in this systematic literature review, highlighting the countries that contributed to the research in this field. China has the highest number of publications (9), reflecting its prominent

role in driving research and development. Following closely are England and Spain, each contributing six studies, indicating strong academic engagement and research activity in these regions.

The USA appeared next with three publications, while Germany contributed two. A significant portion of the remaining countries, including Australia, Austria, Canada, Greece, India, Ireland, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, South Korea, Switzerland, and Taiwan, accounted for a single publication. This widespread geographical spread underscores the global nature of this research topic, with contributions spanning multiple continents and diverse academic communities.

The data suggest that although certain countries, particularly China, England, and Spain, have played leading roles in advancing knowledge in this field, the involvement of numerous other nations highlights the international interest and collaborative potential of this research area. The relatively low contributions from several countries may reflect regional priorities, resource availability, or differing levels of focus on specific subject matters. Overall, the geographical diversity of publications enriches the scope of this review by offering a comprehensive perspective shaped by various cultural, technological and academic contexts.

RQ4.What are the trends in MOOC research?

Figure 4 illustrates the distribution of publications over time, providing a temporal analysis of research activity within the scope of this review. The data reveal that the most recent years have witnessed a significant increase in scholarly output, with 2024 showing the highest number of seven publications, followed closely by 2023 with five and 2021 with six publications. This upward trend suggests a growing interest and rapid development in the field, potentially driven by advancements in technology, emerging research questions, or increased accessibility to relevant tools and methodologies.

Notably, 2022 (five publications) and 2015 (six publications) reflect substantial contributions, indicating periods of heightened academic engagement. In contrast, earlier years, such as 2020, 2018, 2017, and 2016, showed relatively lower publication counts,

Fig. 4 Year-wise distribution of articles

ranging from one to two studies annually. This may signify either limited research activity during these periods or a lag in the dissemination of findings within the field.

Overall, the temporal distribution highlights an accelerating trend in research productivity, particularly from 2021, underscoring the dynamic and evolving nature of this field. This increasing trajectory emphasizes the importance of continued investigation and underscores the need for up-to-date reviews to capture the latest advancements and insights in this area.

RQ5. What specific metrics are used to evaluate MOOC platforms?

Table 3 lists the metrics evaluated in the reviewed studies. This systematic review organizes MOOC evaluation criteria into six overarching themes derived from synthesizing 40 studies (coded A1–A40). Each theme encompasses the sub-criteria identified in the literature, with contributions from specific articles, as outlined below. The themes were designed to capture the multidimensional nature of MOOC effectiveness, spanning the pedagogical, technical, administrative, and learner-centric dimensions. The 1st theme i.e., Course Design & Structure, evaluated the architecture and pedagogical scaffolding of MOOCs. The subcriteria included instructional videos, type of online discussion boards, user interface, feedback mechanisms, flexibility, and blended learning approaches. These elements focus on how course content is organized, delivered, and adapted to learners' needs. The articles contributing to this theme included A3, A8, A10, A11, A12, A20, A37, and A38. The 2nd theme is Learner Engagement & Satisfaction, which examines learner-centric factors such as educators' experience, content complexity, interactivity, stress-related measures, and timing of the course. It emphasizes learner perceptions, motivation, and sociotechnical interactions in MOOCs. The articles contributing to this theme are A5, A6, A7, A9, A16, A17, A18, A26, and A33. The next theme of the evaluation criteria is Instructional Quality. This theme assesses pedagogical practices and instructor effectiveness, including teaching practices, content quality, instructors' oral proficiency, and the alignment of learning activities with educational goals. The articles contributing to this theme included A8, A13, A20, A21, A25, and A37. The next theme includes Assessment and Learning Outcomes. This category evaluates the efficacy of assessments and their alignment with learning objectives. The subcriteria included the type of assessment (for example, MCQs, assignments), skill development, cognitive processes, and semantic structure of learning outcomes. Articles contributing to themes A2, A3, A22, A30, A32, A34, A35, A36, and A15. The next theme of the evaluation criteria includes Technical & Administrative Factors. It addresses operational and infrastructural aspects, such as scalability, accessibility, user experience (UX), data security, and course management strategies. The articles contributing to this theme are A4, A8, A12, A23, A26, A29, A35, and A39. The last theme of the evaluation criteria includes Demographics & Completion Metrics, which focuses on learner diversity, attrition, and participation patterns, including demographic profiles, completion rates, digital literacy levels, and disciplinary variation among users. The articles contributing to this theme are A1, A2, A11, A31, A33, and A40. Uncategorized/NA: a subset of studies (A14, A19, A27) did not align with the six primary themes and were classified as "NA". These did not use any specific parameter to evaluate MOOC platforms but explored MOOC platforms in general, keeping all aspects in view.

These studies highlight the interplay between course design, learner behaviour, instructional rigor, and technical infrastructure in shaping MOOC success. Notably,

Table 3 Metrics evaluated in the reviewed studies

Course design & structure	Learner engagement & satisfaction	Instructional quality	Assessment & learning outcomes	Technical & administrative factors	Demographics & completion metrics	NA
Instructional Videos	Educator's Experience	Instruc-tional Design Quality	Assessment Type	Design Evaluation	Digital Literacy Maturity	NA
Type of Online Discussion Boards	Learner Satisfaction	Teaching Practice	Type Of Online Discussion Boards	Scalability	Digital Skill Diversity	
User Interface and Course Content	Learner Engagement	Pedagogical Practices	Learning Outcomes	Accessibility	Disciplinary Variation	
Interface Design	Organizational	Qualifications And Teaching Effectiveness of Instructors	Course Effectiveness	Technol-ogy And Course Management	Skill Integration	
Course Design	Social And Technical Dimensions	Learning Process	Assessment/ Quality of MCQs	User Experience (Ux)	Skill Prevalence and Variety	
Feedback Mechanism	Content Complexity	Content Quality	Knowledge	Navigation	Completion Rate	
Monitor- ing Progress Throughout the Course	Task Success	Video Quality	Skills And Attitudes	Strategy Development	Demography Analysis	
Course Structure and Content	Time On Task	Learning Activities	Analysis Application	Quality Assessment	Demographic Profile of Users	
Course Description	User Interaction Metrics	Management Of Course	Effectiveness And Value Of MOOC	Reliability	Attrition Rates	
Blended Learning	Stress-Related Measures	Teachers' Oral English Proficiency	Performance Monitoring	Validity	Teaching Quality	
Flexibility	Interest In the Topic	Overall Quali-ty of MOOCs	Quality Of Assignments	Authenticity And Security of User Data	Completion Rates of Video Content	
Openness And Student Cen-tered Learning	Interactiv-ity And Peer Engagement	Instructional Quality	Cognitive Processes		Course Experience	
	Timing Of the Course		Semantic Structure		Course Length	
	Course Satisfaction		Learning Outcome		Total Enrolment	
Articles Include						
A3, A8, A10, A11, A12, A20, A37, A38	A5, A6, A7, A9, A16, A17, A18, A26, A33	A8, A13, A20, A21, A25, A37	A2, A3, A22, A30, A32, A34, A35, A36, A15	A4, A8, A12, A23, A26, A29, A35, A39	A1, A2, A11, A31, A33, A40	A14, A19, A27

themes such as Assessment and Learning Outcomes and Course Design and Structure were most frequently addressed (9–10 articles each), reflecting their centrality in MOOC research. Conversely, Technical & Administrative Factors and Demographics & Completion Metrics were included in fewer studies, suggesting opportunities for deeper exploration. This categorization enables a holistic understanding of MOOC evaluation, bridging theoretical insights (e.g. pedagogical practices) with practical considerations (e.g., scalability and user experience). By mapping articles to themes, the review

underscores recurring challenges (e.g. low completion rates) and innovations (e.g. blended learning models) in the MOOC landscape.

RQ6. Is a qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-method approach employed?

Figure 5 provides an overview of the methodological approaches used in the studies included in this review. The data indicated that most of the reviewed studies (19) employed a Quantitative Method, reflecting a strong preference for numerical data, statistical analysis, and objective measurement. The second most common approach, with 17 studies, was the mixed-method approach, which combines both quantitative and qualitative techniques to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem. Finally, only a small proportion of the studies (4) relied solely on qualitative methods, emphasizing exploratory analysis, in-depth insights, and subjective interpretation. This distribution highlights the dominance of quantitative and mixed-methods research in the field, suggesting a trend toward structured, data-driven investigations while still valuing the integration of qualitative elements for richer contextual understanding.

RQ7. What tools or instruments were used to gather data?

Table 4 provides an overview of the data collection tools used in the studies included in this systematic literature review. Surveys were the most common tools employed in seven studies, indicating a strong reliance on structured questionnaires for quantitative or mixed-method data. Combinations, such as interviews and surveys (six studies) and questionnaires and surveys (three studies), illustrate the frequent integration of multiple techniques to deepen the insights. Other frequently used tools include log data and reviews, each featured in three studies to assess user behaviour, system performance, and existing feedback. Unique combinations, such as co-design artefacts, interviews, log data, questionnaires, recordings, and expert-driven evaluations, such as heuristic evaluation and user studies, underscore methodological creativity. Notably, two studies did not specify their data collection tools, suggesting potential reporting limitations or a reliance on proprietary methods.

To address the gaps identified in the systematic literature review (SLR) and synthesize existing evaluation practices, the following integrated framework was theoretically grounded: this framework holistically combines pedagogical, technical, and

Fig. 5 Method used by the selected studies

Table 4 Data collection tools used by the selected studies

Data Collection Tool	Number
Surveys	7
Interviews, Surveys	6
Log Data	3
Questionnaire, Survey	3
Reviews	3
Interviews, Reviews	2
Questionnaire	2
Co- Design Artefacts, Interviews, Log Data, Questionnaire, Recording	1
Content Analysis, Interviews, Survey	1
Evaluate Comments	1
Expert Evaluations, Reviews	1
Heuristic Evaluation, User Studies	1
In-Course Quizzes, Free Text Feedback, Surveys	1
Interviews	1
Biosensors, Surveys	1
Log Data, Reviews	1
Manual Coding By Human Evaluators And Automated Evaluation Of MCQs	1
Questionnaire, Surveys, User Study	1
Simulation Experiments	1
NA	2

Fig. 6 Integrative model

learner-centric dimensions while incorporating accessibility, scalability, and emerging trends in digital education.

Framework Components.

The framework comprises six core dimensions, each with subcriteria and aligned evaluation metrics, as shown in Fig. 6. These dimensions are interconnected, ensuring a balanced assessment of MOOC platforms.

5 Integrated-framework for the evaluation of MOOC platforms

To comprehensively evaluate MOOC platforms, a theoretically grounded integrative framework was derived from a systematic analysis of existing studies. This framework, illustrated in Fig. 6, identifies six key dimensions that are critical for assessing the effectiveness and quality of MOOCs. Each dimension was elaborated with specific constructs and evaluation metrics grounded in prior research to provide a robust and actionable evaluation tool. Furthermore, future studies can utilise this model by integrating qualitative, quantitative, and mixed data to evaluate MOOC platforms by applying statistical techniques, thematic and content analysis, and text mining approaches.

The integrative framework (Fig. 7) synthesizes the findings from a sample of studies to address the multifaceted nature of MOOC platforms. The six dimensions include Course Structure & Design, Learner Engagement & Satisfaction, Instructional Quality, Assessment & Learning Outcomes, Technical & Administrative Factors, and Demographics & Completion Metrics, which collectively capture the pedagogical, technical,

Fig. 7 Integrative model

and user-centric aspects of MOOCs. Each dimension is operationalised through constructs and measurable metrics, as detailed in Tables 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10, ensuring a holistic evaluation approach.

5.1 Dimension 1: course structure & design

The “Course Structure & Design” dimension evaluates the foundational architecture of a MOOC, which directly influences the learning experience. The instructional Design & Multimedia Elements assess the quality and accessibility of multimedia resources, which are critical for engaging diverse learners and accommodating different learning styles. For instance, high-quality videos and interactive discussion boards can enhance students’ comprehension and retention. Communication, Feedback and Progress Monitoring focus on interaction channels, ensuring that learners receive timely feedback and track their progress, fostering a sense of agency. Interfaces and navigation examine usability, as poorly designed interfaces can frustrate users and hinder learning. Course Content & Organization ensures that the content is logically sequenced and modular, supporting coherence and adaptability to varied educational contexts. Finally, Flexibility & Student-Centred Learning highlights MOOC’s ability to cater to individual pacing and preferences, a hallmark of open education. High scores in video quality or discussion board engagement suggest that a MOOC is visually and socially engaging, whereas poor navigation ease might indicate usability barriers to learning. Studies such as A3 and A20 underscore the importance of these constructs across contexts, suggesting their universal relevance in MOOC design.

Table 5 Dimension 1

Construct	Description	Evaluation metrics	Evaluation sub-metrics	Studies
Instructional Design & Multi-media Elements	Includes instructional videos, animations, and accessibility features.	Video quality, discussion board quality	Video resolution (HD/SD) Audio clarity, caption availability, visual aids (slides, annotations), Instructor presentation. Relevance of course, moderator presence, timeliness of responses, tone and language.	A3, A8, A10, A11, A12, A20, A37, A38
Communication, Feedback and Progress Monitoring	Incorporates discussion boards, peer reviews, and real-time feedback.	Discussion board engagement, feedback mechanism	Number of posts per learner, number of replies, frequency of visits to the board, thread length, peer-to-peer interaction rate.	A3, A8, A10, A11, A12, A20, A37, A38
Interface & Navigation	Covers platform usability, layout, and accessibility features.	User interface satisfaction, ease of navigation	Visual appeal, font and readability, layout consistency, color scheme Overall user satisfaction. Finding a course, accessing course materials, submitting an assignment, viewing grades.	A3, A8, A10, A11, A12, A20, A37, A38
Course Content & Organization	Examines modular organization, logical sequencing, and blended learning strategies.	Content organization, adaptability	Is it modular? Are topics logically sequenced? Are objectives stated clearly? Multi-device compatibility.	A3, A8, A10, A11, A12, A20, A37, A38
Flexibility & Student-Centered Learning	Encompasses adaptive learning, open educational resources, and student autonomy.	Self-paced learning effectiveness, customization tools	Were you able to complete the course at your own pace? Did the flexibility help you retain more information?, first login and last login. Adjustable text size, theme switching (dark/light), custom learning path, bookmarking content.	A3, A8, A10, A11, A12, A20, A37, A38

Table 6 Dimension 2

Construct	Description	Evaluation metrics	Evaluation sub-metrics	Studies
Learner Satisfaction & Motivation	Assesses course expectations, content quality, and perceived value.	Learner ratings, likelihood of recommendation	Instructor quality, content quality, platform usability, learning outcomes. Net promoter score (NPS)	A5, A6, A7, A9, A16, A17, A18, A26, A33
Engagement & Interactive Participation	Covers discussion forums, collaborative activities, and time spent on tasks.	Participation frequency, active time on platform	Number of logins per week/month, total time logged in, average time per session.	A5, A6, A7, A9, A16, A17, A18, A26, A33
Social & Technical Dimensions	Focuses on digital community interaction and technological tools.	Forum activity, tool usability	Number of posts/replies per learner, ratio of replies to posts, number of threads initiated, frequency of unanswered posts. Quiz interface	A5, A6, A7, A9, A16, A17, A18, A26, A33
Support & Infrastructure	Examines administrative support, technical resources, and platform scalability.	Support response time, system reliability	Response time to queries. Compare performance across platforms, login failures, crashes, broken links, total time server down.	A5, A6, A7, A9, A16, A17, A18, A26, A33
Cognitive Load & Stress Factors	Evaluates perceived workload, content complexity, and stress-related issues.	Self-reported stress levels, cognitive engagement	Perceived stress scale (PSS) or self-made MOOC stress checklist. Cognitive engagement questionnaire	A5, A6, A7, A9, A16, A17, A18, A26, A33

Table 7 Dimension 3

Construct	Description	Evaluation metrics	Evaluation sub-metrics	Studies
Instructional & Content Quality	Focuses on curriculum structure, multimedia integration, and content clarity.	Course content comprehensive-ness, accuracy	Topics covered, depth of coverage, relevance to subject domain. Review course materials (videos, texts, quizzes). Cross-check with trusted academic sources (journals, textbooks). Mark errors or outdated content.	A8, A13, A20, A21, A25, A37
Teaching & Pedagogical Practices	Assesses educator delivery, engagement techniques, and assessment strategies.	Teaching effectiveness, learner interaction	Clarity of explanations, responsiveness to learner needs, assessment strategies. replies, likes, questions asked.	A8, A13, A20, A21, A25, A37
Instructor Qualifications & Effectiveness	Evaluates academic background, teaching experience, and content delivery skills.	Instructor ratings, course completion correlation	Communication clarity, subject knowledge, instructors academic background, teaching experience and content delivery skills. Instructor rating per course, completion rate per course.	A8, A13, A20, A21, A25, A37
Learning Process & Management	Covers cognitive and practical learning activities, comprehension, and application.	Learner progress tracking, knowledge application success	Completion of modules, time spent per section, quiz attempts	A8, A13, A20, A21, A25, A37
Overall MOOC Quality	Integrates instructional quality, learner outcomes, and platform effectiveness.	User satisfaction surveys, dropout rates	Interface, content, instructor, learning outcomes. Enrollment vs. completion analysis.	A8, A13, A20, A21, A25, A37

Table 8 Dimension 4

Construct	Description	Evaluation metrics	Evaluation sub-metrics	Studies
Learning Outcomes & Knowledge Gain	Defines intended skills, competencies, and concept mastery.	Post-course assessment scores, knowledge retention	Final test or exam Analysis.	A2, A3, A22, A30, A32, A34, A35, A36, A15
Course Effectiveness & Value	Evaluates alignment with educational goals and real-world applicability.	Completion rates, learner testimonials	Enrollment vs. certification data. Qualitative feedback.	A2, A3, A22, A30, A32, A34, A35, A36, A15
Assessment Design & Validity	Examines quizzes, assignments, and formative evaluations.	Assessment accuracy, grading consistency	MCQs, peer-reviewed, auto-graded code, essays.	A2, A3, A22, A30, A32, A34, A35, A36, A15
Cognitive Processes & Skill Development	Analyzes problem-solving, critical thinking, and skill application.	Performance in applied tasks, project success rates	Application of knowledge, creativity, relevance.	A2, A3, A22, A30, A32, A34, A35, A36, A15
Semantic & Content Structure	Focuses on logical sequencing and clarity of instructional materials.	Content readability, instructional coherence	Readability score analysis, text lectures, PDFs, pages. Are topics logically sequenced, Are concepts scaffolded properly?	A2, A3, A22, A30, A32, A34, A35, A36, A15

5.2 Dimension 2: learner engagement & satisfaction

This dimension captures the learners’ active involvement and emotional responses to MOOCs. Learner Satisfaction & Motivation measure whether the course meets expectations and provides value, influencing retention and word-of-mouth promotion. Engagement and Interactive Participation evaluate how learners interact with their content and peers, as active participation often correlates with deeper learning. Social and Technical Dimensions assess community-building potential and tool functionality, which are

Table 9 Dimension 5

Construct	Description	Evaluation metrics	Evaluation sub-metrics	Studies
Platform Scalability & Reliability	Ensures seamless performance under varying user loads.	System uptime, error reports	Login failures, content not loading, server crash.	A4, A8, A12, A23, A26, A29, A35, A39
Accessibility & User Experience	Ensures inclusivity and ease of use across diverse learners.	Compliance with accessibility standards, assistive tool integration	Color contrast, keyboard navigation.	A4, A8, A12, A23, A26, A29, A35, A39
Technology & Course Management	Covers system stability, content updating, and administrative processes.	Update platform, ease of content updates	Time taken to update videos, quizzes, text.	A4, A8, A12, A23, A26, A29, A35, A39
Security & Data Protection	Focuses on user data privacy and authentication measures.	Data security compliance, user trust levels	Does platform follow global data protection standards, secure authentication, personal data is safe on this platform.	A4, A8, A12, A23, A26, A29, A35, A39
Strategic Planning & Course Improvement	Addresses curriculum planning and continuous improvement initiatives.	Course revision frequency, adaptation to learner feedback	Content version tracking, feedback action mapping	A4, A8, A12, A23, A26, A29, A35, A39

Table 10 Dimension 6

Construct	Description	Evaluation metrics	Evaluation sub-metrics	Studies
Digital Literacy & Skill Diversity	Assesses learner proficiency with digital tools and the range of digital competencies.	Self-reported digital proficiency, performance in tech-based tasks	Learners digital skill	A1, A2, A11, A31, A33, A40
Completion & Attrition Rates	Examines learner retention, drop-off points, and factors affecting course completion.	Completion percentages, drop-out analysis	Enrollment vs. Completion Data Analysis, learner activity over time.	A1, A2, A11, A31, A33, A40
Demographic Analysis	Analyzes learner characteristics, including age, education, and geographic distribution.	Learner segmentation statistics, participation trends	Demographic data (age, region, profession, education level), Time-Based User Activity Analysis	A1, A2, A11, A31, A33, A40
Course Experience & Perceived Value	Captures learner satisfaction and course effectiveness based on user feedback.	Post-course surveys, perceived learning value	Satisfaction, perceived impact, and suggestions, skill gain, job relevance, knowledge improvement.	A1, A2, A11, A31, A33, A40
Enrollment & Engagement Metrics	Tracks registration numbers, active participation, and interaction trends.	Total enrollments, participation frequency, engagement duration	Cumulative enrollment numbers from the LMS, Logins per week, forum posts per user, average time/session, average time/module.	A1, A2, A11, A31, A33, A40

vital for collaborative learning in online settings. Support and infrastructure ensure that learners have reliable technical and administrative backing, thereby reducing frustration. Finally, Cognitive Load & Stress Factors address the balance between challenge and overwhelming, as excessive complexity can deter completion. High participation frequency and positive learner ratings indicate a motivating and engaging MOOC, whereas low forum activity might suggest weak community interaction. If the support response time is slow or stress levels are high, learners may disengage, highlighting areas for improvement. Studies A16 and A26 emphasised the role of engagement in satisfaction, reinforcing the predictive power of this dimension for MOOC success.

5.3 Dimension 3: instructional quality

Instructional quality is central to educational impact, focusing on teaching efficacy and content delivery. Instructional and Content Quality ensure that the materials are clear and comprehensive, forming the backbone of learning. Teaching and Pedagogical Practices evaluate how instructors engage learners and structure assessments, which are critical for maintaining students' interest and understanding. Instructors' Qualifications and Effectiveness assess the educator's expertise and delivery, as credibility enhances trust in the educator. The Learning Process & Management track how well learners assimilate and apply knowledge, reflecting the success of instruction. Overall MOOC Quality ties these elements to broader outcomes, such as satisfaction and retention. High teaching effectiveness and accurate content suggest a strong instructional foundation, whereas low instructor ratings or high dropout rates may indicate delivery issues. For instance, strong correlations between instructor effectiveness and completion (noted in A21) imply that qualified instructors drive success, making this a key factor for MOOC evaluation.

5.4 Dimension 4: assessment & learning outcomes

This dimension measures a MOOC's ability to achieve educational goals through robust assessment and tangible outcomes. Learning Outcomes & Knowledge Gain quantify skill and concept mastery, which is the ultimate aim of education. Course Effectiveness and Value assess practical relevance and goal alignment, ensuring real-world impact. Assessment Design & Validity ensures that evaluations are fair, reliable, and critical for credibility. Cognitive Processes & Skill Development focuses on higher-order thinking, which is essential for lifelong learning. The semantic and content structures ensure that the materials logically and clearly support these outcomes. Strong post-course scores and project success indicate effective learning, whereas inconsistent grading or low completion rates may reflect assessment flaws. Studies such as A34 highlight the link between clear content and outcomes, suggesting that well-designed assessments drive measurable improvements.

5.5 Dimension 5: technical & administrative factors

Technical and administrative factors underpin MOOC's operational success of MOOCs. Platform Scalability & Reliability ensure that the system handles large user bases without crashing, which is vital for a global reach. Accessibility and User Experience make the platform inclusive and broaden its audience. Technology and Course Management assess administrative efficiency, such as seamlessly updating content. Security and Data Protection safeguard user trust, which is non-negotiable in a digital environment. Strategic Planning and Course Improvement reflect a platform's adaptability to evolving needs. High uptime and accessibility compliance suggest a robust and inclusive platform, whereas frequent errors or poor security could erode trust. Regular course revisions (noted in A23) indicate responsiveness and enhanced, long-term viability.

5.6 Dimension 6: demographics & completion metrics

This dimension profiles learners and their completion patterns, offering insights into reach and efficacy. Digital Literacy & Skill Diversity assess technological readiness, which is crucial for online success. Completion and Attrition Rates measure retention,

which is a persistent challenge in MOOCs. Demographic Analysis revealed audience diversity and inclusivity. Course Experience and Perceived Value gauge subjective success, whereas enrolment and engagement metrics quantify scale and activity. High completion rates and diverse demographics suggest broad appeal and effectiveness, whereas low digital proficiency or high attrition may indicate barriers. A strong engagement duration reflects sustained interest, which is aligned with the findings of A33.

6 Findings & discussion

This systematic review revealed that MOOC evaluation research is characterized by diverse frameworks and evaluation criteria. The most commonly employed frameworks or models include Kirkpatrick's Model and the Quality Matters Evaluation Framework, and many researchers have combined these with other approaches to address the multifaceted nature of MOOC assessment. The literature indicates that evaluation dimensions extend across several key areas, including the structure and design of courses, degree of learner engagement, quality of instructional delivery, and effectiveness of assessment methods. Technical and administrative factors also play crucial roles in determining the overall performance and accessibility of MOOC platforms. The review reports diverse patterns in the geographical distribution of research on MOOC platform evaluation, with a pronounced dominance of countries such as China, England, Spain, and the USA, with sparse representation from Global South regions, including Africa, parts of Asia, and Latin America. The limited representation of the Global South has also been reported by earlier bibliometric and systematic review studies, which highlight the persistent dominance of Global North regions in digital education scholarship [74, 75]. Several compounding factors contribute to this disparity, including infrastructural and connectivity challenges in many Global South countries that restrict both MOOC adoption and the capacity for extensive research output [76, 77], constrained research funding and institutional capacity that reduce the volume of high-impact, indexed publications from these regions [78], the reliance of indexing databases like Web of Science on English-language journals that further exclude regional literature [74], and in some contexts, policy and awareness gaps that mean that research emphasis remains on MOOC adoption rather than systematic evaluation [79].

The results reveal significant fragmentation in MOOC evaluation research, with many studies relying on isolated or narrowly focused criteria for evaluation. This fragmentation hinders effective comparisons across platforms, the generalisation of findings, and the development of standardised benchmarks. Consequently, the scattered nature of existing frameworks also limits the ability of researchers, educators, and platform developers to generate cohesive insights or make informed decisions. Addressing this challenge requires integrative frameworks that unify pedagogical, technical, and learner-centred dimensions. The proposed framework through this review aims to fill this gap by synthesizing diverse evaluation efforts into a standardized framework that reduces subjective bias and facilitates robust, comparative research across different platforms and regions. This approach strengthens the potential for a consistent and meaningful evaluation of MOOC platform quality on a global scale.

Thus, the framework offers a robust and multifaceted tool for assessing, validating, and enhancing the quality of these platforms by systematically evaluating them across six critical dimensions: Course Structure & Design, Learner Engagement & Satisfaction,

Instructional Quality, Assessment & Learning Outcomes, Technical & Administrative Factors, and Demographics & Completion Metrics. The framework integrates diverse parameters, ranging from pedagogical effectiveness (e.g. instructional design and assessment validity) to technical robustness (e.g. scalability and accessibility) and learner-centric factors (e.g. engagement and digital literacy), into a cohesive evaluation system. By applying this framework, researchers and educators can prove the efficacy of specific MOOC features, such as adaptive learning or social interaction tools, through empirical testing of hypotheses such as those listed above. For instance, it enables the measurement of how well-designed assessments (Dimension 4) translate into skill application or how reliable platforms (Dimension 5) support learners in low-resource settings, providing actionable insights for improvement. Its comprehensive constructs and metrics allow stakeholders to pinpoint strengths, identify weaknesses, and tailor MOOC offerings to diverse populations, ultimately advancing online education through evidence-based evaluations and innovations.

The framework can be further validated by conducting research using feasible validation strategies to strengthen its reliability and applicability through different approaches. For example, cross-sectional surveys can be developed using Likert-scale items for each dimension and distributed to MOOC learners across diverse platforms, with Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) employed to assess whether the six dimensions emerge as distinct yet related constructs, thereby testing construct validity. In addition, multi-platform comparative studies could be conducted by applying the framework to various MOOCs and comparing the resulting scores with benchmarks such as completion rates, learner satisfaction, and rankings to assess criterion-related validity.

Additionally, learning analytics and platform data mining offer valuable opportunities, as several MOOC providers allow access to anonymized log data, clickstream activity, and forum participation, enabling an objective comparison of behavioral engagement measures with survey-based data.

Finally, expert panel and Delphi studies involving MOOC designers, platform managers, and online learning researchers could be used to reach a consensus on the clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness of the framework, ensuring its content validity. Taken together, these approaches represent practical pathways for future empirical validation, supporting the refinement and eventual broader applicability of this framework.

Furthermore, the framework can also be empirically tested based on the assumptions or hypotheses presented below and is not limited to such hypotheses; however, researchers can utilise the framework to apply it as per the platform demands.

The six dimensions identified and represented in Fig. 7 form the building blocks for the theoretically grounded integrated framework for evaluating MOOC platforms. The integration of these six dimensions towards evolving a substantial framework with the potential to facilitate MOOC platform evaluation for guiding the choices towards selecting and opting for more potential MOOCs. These platforms possess identical characteristic features, which justifies the integration of different dimensions into a single integrated framework. These dimensions interact with each other to provide a holistic assessment. For example, technical and administrative factors (Dimension 5) directly influence learner engagement and satisfaction (Dimension 2), whereas course structure and design (Dimension 1) set the foundation for effective instructional quality (Dimension 3).

The framework is designed to be flexible and adaptable across different MOOC platforms, learner demographics, and institutional goals. While it can be empirically tested, it serves as a robust theoretical foundation for researchers and educators to validate the framework in diverse educational and geographical settings in the future. The study proposes seven hypotheses (H1 to H7) that can be leveraged to investigate these dynamics, offering a roadmap for empirical studies to validate, refine, and extend the framework's applicability.

H1: MOOCs incorporating adaptive learning features within their *Course Structure & Design* (Dimension 1) will exhibit significantly higher *Learning Outcomes & Knowledge Gain* (Dimension 4), as measured by post-course assessment scores and knowledge retention, compared to MOOCs without such features.

H2: The level of *Social & Technical Dimensions* engagement (Dimension 2), such as forum activity and tool usability, positively correlates with *Completion & Attrition Rates* (Dimension 6) in MOOCs, with stronger effects observed in culturally diverse learner populations.

H3: MOOCs with human instructors demonstrating high *Instructor Qualifications & Effectiveness* (Dimension 3), as assessed by instructor ratings, will result in lower dropout rates and higher *Overall MOOC Quality* satisfaction scores than fully automated MOOCs.

H4: The quality of *Assessment Design & Validity* (Dimension 4), measured by assessment accuracy and grading consistency, will positively predict learners' long-term *Cognitive Processes & Skill Development*, as evidenced by their performance in applied professional tasks six months post-course.

H5: MOOC platforms with higher scores for *Platform Scalability & Reliability and Accessibility & User Experience* (Dimension 5), such as system uptime and assistive tool integration, will demonstrate greater learner satisfaction and completion rates in low-resource settings than platforms with lower scores.

H6: Learners with higher *Digital Literacy & Skill Diversity* (Dimension 6), as measured by self-reported proficiency, will exhibit significantly higher *Engagement & Interactive Participation* (Dimension 2) and *Completion & Attrition Rates* (Dimension 6) across all age groups, with the strongest effects among older adults.

H7: MOOCs implementing frequent *Strategic Planning & Course Improvement* updates (Dimension 5) based on learner feedback will show a significant increase in *Learner Satisfaction & Motivation* (Dimension 2) and reduced dropout rates over successive iterations compared to MOOCs with static designs.

7 Conclusion

The analysis confirmed that while MOOCs hold significant promise for democratizing education, their success hinges on the ability to evaluate them comprehensively and effectively. The theoretically grounded integrated evaluation framework synthesizes key dimensions that bridge the gap between theory and practice, including pedagogical, technical, and learner-centric evaluation dimensions. The framework not only addresses the variability in current evaluation practices but also provides a roadmap for standardizing assessments across diverse educational settings. Overall, the study concludes that a holistic approach to MOOC evaluation is essential for measuring learning outcomes,

improving course design, and enhancing user experience, ultimately contributing to the sustainability and effectiveness of online-education platforms.

7.1 Practical implications

The findings of this study have significant implications for various stakeholders involved in the MOOC ecosystem. Educators are encouraged to design courses that are not only robust in content but also engaging and adaptable to meet diverse learner needs. MOOC providers can leverage this integrated framework to enhance user experience by incorporating interactive features and adaptive technologies that address common challenges, such as low retention rates. Policymakers can use these insights to develop regulatory standards and guidelines that promote quality and accessibility in online education. By aligning instructional practices with standardized evaluation metrics, institutions can improve course delivery and support lifelong learning initiatives.

7.2 Theoretical implications

From a theoretical standpoint, this study contributes to the advancement of MOOC research by offering a comprehensive synthesis of evaluation criteria and an integrated framework that unifies diverse assessment approaches.

This framework bridges the gap between existing pedagogical theories and practical evaluation metrics and provides a benchmark for future studies. This encourages researchers to move beyond isolated evaluation dimensions and consider a more interconnected approach that encompasses pedagogical quality, technical robustness and learner engagement. This holistic perspective enriches academic discourse and lays the foundation for developing more rigorous and standardized assessment frameworks for online education.

7.3 Limitations and scope for future research

Despite its contributions, this study has several limitations that should be addressed in future research. The primary reliance on literature sourced from a single database may have limited the breadth of the review, potentially excluding relevant studies available in other repositories. This may exclude insights from grey literature and non-English studies. Additionally, the cross-sectional nature of the analysis restricts insights into the long-term evolution of MOOC effectiveness. Future research should incorporate a wider range of data sources and adopt a longitudinal approach to capture dynamic changes in MOOC evaluations over time. Furthermore, exploring the impact of emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and immersive learning environments, could provide deeper insights into the future trajectory of MOOC assessment.

Appendix

Code	Author	Evaluation Criteria
A1	Lin, (2014)	Shannon Diversity Index, Simpson Diversity Index, Coverage Rate, Skills Richness, Skills Combination Index, And Digital Literacy Maturity Model
A2	Strehlow et al., (2014)	Completion Rate, Assessment Type, Course Satisfaction, Demography Analysis, Course Design And Delivery
A3	Cho et al., (2014)	Course Structure, Instructional Videos, Type Of Assessment, Type Of Online Discussion Boards

Code	Author	Evaluation Criteria
A4	Topali et al., (2014)	Design Evaluation, Scalability, Learner Engagement
A5	Alghamdi, (2014)	Learners' Satisfaction, Video Quality, Educators' Experience, And Quality Of Information
A6	Dagenais et al., (2014)	Satisfaction, Course Content, Technical, Organizational, And Social Dimensions
A7	Coad et al., (2023)	Course Effectiveness, Participant Satisfaction, Attrition Rates, Content Complexity
A8	Wang, (2023)	Teaching Practices, Course Content, Instructional Design, Interface Design, Technology And Course Management
A9	Shah et al., (2023)	Pedagogical Practices, User Engagement
A10	Iniesto et al., (2023)	Course Design And Accessibility, Feedback Mechanism, Monitoring Progress Throughout The Course
A11	Eglseer, (2023)	Course Structure And Content, Demographic Profile Of Users
A12	Królak & Zajac, (2024)	Accessibility, User Interface And Course Content
A13	Liu, (2022)	Teaching Effectiveness, Learning Process
A14	Ross et al., (2022)	Na
A15	Ortego, Pascual, (2015)	Cognitive Processes, Semantic Structure, Learning Gains
A16	Liapis et al. (2023)	Task Success, Time On Task, User Interaction Matrics, Stress-Related Measures
A17	Moustakas and Kalina (2022)	Interest In The Topic, Quality Of Resources, Interactivity And Peer Engagement, Timing Of The Course
A18	Tzeng et al. (2022)	Student Satisfaction
A19	Rong et al. (2021)	Na
A20	Wang et al. (2021)	Instructional Design Quality, Course Description, Videos And Materials, Learning Activities
A21	Luo and Ye (2021)	Qualifications And Teaching Effectiveness Of Instructors, Content Quality, Pedagogical Approach, User Interface, Accessibility, Management Of Course, Teachers' Oral English Proficiency, Instructional Design
A22	Launois et al. (2021)	Learning Outcomes
A23	Molanes-López et al. (2021)	Accessibility Of Video Content
A24	Nie et al. (2021)	Overall Quality Of Moocs
A25	Alturkistani et al. (2020)	Pedagogical Practices
A26	Liu et al. (2020)	User Experience (Ux), Interface Design, Navigation, Layout And Multimedia Content
A27	Smith-Lickess et al. (2019)	Na
A28	Samoila et al. (2019)	Effectiveness Of The Course
A29	Park et al. (2019)	Accessibility
A30	Costello et al. (2018)	Assessment/Quality Of Mcqs
A31	Xie (2019)	Completion Rates Of Video Content
A32	Meinert et al. (2018)	Knowledge, Skills And Attitudes
A33	Gil-Jaurena et al. (2017)	Learner Satisfaction, Course Experience, Demographic Profile Of Participants, Completion Rates
A34	Ruipérez-Valiente et al. (2017)	ANALYSIS Application
A35	Chapman et al. (2016)	Effectiveness And Value Of Moocs, Performance Monitoring, Strategy Development
A36	Coelho et al. (2015)	Completion Rates And Quality Of Assignments
A37	Lowenthal and Hodges (2015)	Course Design, Instructional Quality
A38	Yousef et al. (2015)	Blended Learning, Flexibility, Quality Of Content, Instructional Design, Openness And Student Centered Learning
A39	Ramírez-Fernández and Silvera (2015)	Quality Assessment, Reliability, Validity, Authenticity And Security Of User Data
A40	Jordan (2015)	Completion Rates, Course Length, Assessment Type, Attrition Rates, Total Enrolment

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